

A Study of AH-Substructures in n-Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to define and study for the first time AH-substructures in n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces such as weak/strong AH-subspaces, and weak/strong AH-linear transformations between two n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces. Also, this paper introduces some elementary properties of these concepts.

Keywords: n-Refined Neutrosophic vector space , AH-subspace, AHS-subspace, AH-linear transformation.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy as a new kind of logic, concerns with nature, origin, and scope of neutralities became a rich material in algebra. Many algebraic structures have been defined and handled such as neutrosophic rings, neutrosophic modules, and neutrosophic vector spaces. See [8,9,10,11,12,14]. More generalizations came to light such as refined neutrosophic rings, n-refined neutrosophic rings, and n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces. See [3,5,6,7,15,16].

AH-substructures were defined for the first time in neutrosophic rings [1]. Then they were defined in n-refined neutrosophic rings, and neutrosophic vector spaces in [2,4]. AH-structures consist of similar objects, each object has the same structure. For example in a neutrosophic vector space $V(I) = V + VI$, AH-subspace is a non empty subset with form $T = M + NI$, where M, N are two classical subspaces in V . Also, AHS-linear transformations were defined by similar aspect [4]. AH-substructures illustrate a bridge between neutrosophic structures and classical algebraic structures and help us to use classical methods in neutrosophical studies.

This article defines some AH-substructures in n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces. Concepts such as AH-subspaces, and AH-linear transformations. Also, it presents some interesting properties and theorems concerning these concepts.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1: [15]

Let $(R, +, \times)$ be a ring and $I_k; 1 \leq k \leq n$ be n indeterminacies. We define $R_n(I) = \{a_0 + a_1I + \dots + a_nI_n; a_i \in R\}$ to be n-refined neutrosophic ring.

Definition 2.2: [15]

(a) Let $R_n(I)$ be an n-refined neutrosophic ring and $P = \sum_{i=0}^n P_i I_i = \{a_0 + a_1 I + \dots + a_n I_n; a_i \in P_i\}$, where P_i is a subset of R , we define P to be an AH-subring if P_i is a subring of R for all i . AHS-subring is defined by the condition $P_i = P_j$ for all i, j .

(b) P is an AH-ideal if P_i are two sided ideals of R for all i , the AHS-ideal is defined by the condition $P_i = P_j$ for all i, j .

Definition 2.3 : [8]

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over the field K then $(V(I), +, \cdot)$ is called a weak neutrosophic vector space over the field K , and it is called a strong neutrosophic vector space if it is a vector space over the neutrosophic field $K(I)$.

Definition 2.4 : [8]

Let $V(I)$ be a strong neutrosophic vector space over the neutrosophic field $K(I)$ and $W(I)$ be a non empty set of $V(I)$, then $W(I)$ is called a strong neutrosophic subspace if $W(I)$ is itself a strong neutrosophic vector space.

Definition 2.5: [14]

Let $(K, +, \cdot)$ be a field, we say that $K_n(I) = K + KI_1 + \dots + KI_n = \{a_0 + a_1 I_1 + \dots + a_n I_n; a_i \in K\}$ is an n-refined neutrosophic field.

It is clear that $K_n(I)$ is an n-refined neutrosophic ring but not a field in classical meaning.

Definition 2.6 : [14]

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over the field K . Then we say that $V_n(I) = V + VI_1 + \dots + VI_n = \{x_0 + x_1 I_1 + \dots + x_n I_n; x_i \in V\}$ is a weak n-refined neutrosophic vector space over the field K . Elements of $V_n(I)$ are called n-refined neutrosophic vectors, elements of K are called scalars.

If we take scalars from the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, we say that $V_n(I)$ is a strong n-refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$. Elements of $K_n(I)$ are called n-refined neutrosophic scalars.

Definition 2.7: [14]

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak n-refined neutrosophic vector space over the field K , a nonempty subset $W_n(I)$ is called a weak n-refined neutrosophic subspace of $V_n(I)$ if $W_n(I)$ is a subspace of $V_n(I)$ itself.

Definition 2.8: [14]

Let $V_n(I)$ be a strong n-refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, a nonempty subset $W_n(I)$ is called a strong n-refined neutrosophic subspace of $V_n(I)$ if $W_n(I)$ is a submodule of $V_n(I)$ itself.

Definition 2.9: [4]

Let $V(I) = V + VI$ be a strong/weak neutrosophic vector space, the set

$S = P + QI = \{x + yI; x \in P, y \in Q\}$, where P and Q are subspaces of V is called an AH-subspace of $V(I)$.

If $P = Q$ then S is called an AHS-subspace of $V(I)$.

Definition 2.10: [4]

(a) Let V and W be two vector spaces, $L_V: V \rightarrow W$ be a linear transformation. The AHS-linear transformation can be defined as follows:

$$L: V(I) \rightarrow W(I); L(a + bI) = L_V(a) + L_V(b)I.$$

(b) If $S = P + QI$ is an AH-subspace of $V(I)$, $L(S) = L_V(P) + L_V(Q)I$.

3. Main discussion

Definition 3.1:

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over a field K , $V_n(I)$ be the corresponding weak n -refined neutrosophic vector space over K . Consider the set $\{M_i; 0 \leq i \leq n\}$, where M_i is a subspace of V . We say:

$M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n = \{m_0 + m_1I_1 + \dots + m_nI_n; m_i \in M_i\}$ is a weak n -refined AH-subspace of the weak n -refined vector space $V_n(I)$.

We say that $M_n(I)$ is a weak n -refined AH-subspace if $M_j = M_i$ for all i, j .

Definition 3.2:

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over a field K , $V_n(I)$ be the corresponding strong n -refined neutrosophic vector space over the n -refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$. Consider the set $\{M_i; 0 \leq i \leq n\}$, where M_i is a subspace of V . We say:

$M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n = \{m_0 + m_1I_1 + \dots + m_nI_n; m_i \in M_i\}$ is a strong n -refined AH-subspace of the strong n -refined vector space $V_n(I)$.

We say that $M_n(I)$ is a strong n -refined AH-subspace if $M_j = M_i$ for all i, j .

Theorem 3.3:

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over a field K , $V_n(I)$ be the corresponding weak n -refined neutrosophic vector space over K , $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n$ be a weak n -refined AH-subspace. Then

(a) $M_n(I)$ is a vector subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) If X_i is a bases of M_i , $X = \bigcup_{i=0}^n X_iI_i$ is a bases of $M_n(I)$.

(c) $\dim(M_n(I)) = \sum_{i=0}^n \dim(M_i)$.

Proof:

(a) Let $x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_iI_i, y = \sum_{i=0}^n b_iI_i; b_i, a_i \in M_i$ be two arbitrary elements in $M_n(I)$, r be an arbitrary element in K , we have:

$$x + y = \sum_{i=0}^n (a_i + b_i)I_i \in M_n(I), \text{ since } a_i + b_i \in M_i \text{ because } M_i \text{ is a subspace of } V.$$

$$r \cdot x = \sum_{i=0}^n ra_iI_i \in M_n(I), \text{ since } ra_i \in M_i \text{ because } M_i \text{ is a subspace of } V. \text{ Thus } M_n(I) \text{ is a vector subspace of } V_n(I).$$

(b) Suppose that $X_0 = \{x_1^{(0)}, \dots, x_{s_0}^{(0)}\}, X_1 = \{x_1^{(1)}, \dots, x_{s_1}^{(1)}\}, \dots, X_n = \{x_1^{(n)}, \dots, x_{s_n}^{(n)}\}$, let $x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_iI_i$ be an arbitrary element of $M_n(I)$, since X_i is a basis of M_i for all i . We can write:

$a_i = \sum_{j=0}^{s_i} t_j^{(i)} x_j^{(i)}$; $t_j \in K$, so $x = \sum_{j=0}^{s_0} t_j^{(0)} x_j^{(0)} + \sum_{j=0}^{s_1} t_j^{(1)} x_j^{(1)} I_1 + \dots + \sum_{j=0}^{s_n} t_j^{(n)} x_j^{(n)} I_n$. This implies that X is a generating set of $M_n(I)$.

Now we prove that X is linearly independent. For our purpose we assume

$\sum_{j=0}^{s_0} t_j^{(0)} x_j^{(0)} + \sum_{j=0}^{s_1} t_j^{(1)} x_j^{(1)} I_1 + \dots + \sum_{j=0}^{s_n} t_j^{(n)} x_j^{(n)} I_n = 0$, by definition of n -refined vector space we find

$\sum_{j=0}^{s_i} t_j^{(i)} x_j^{(i)}$ for all i , hence $t_j^{(i)} = 0$ for all i, j , since each X_i is linearly independent itself. Thus our proof is complete.

(c) It holds directly from (b).

Example 3.4:

Let $V = R^2$ be a vector space over the field R , $V_2(I) = R_2^2(I) = \{(a_0, b_0) + (a_1, b_1)I_1 + (a_2, b_2)I_2; a_i, b_i \in R\}$ be the corresponding weak 2-refined neutrosophic vector space over the field R , we have:

(a) $M = \langle (1, 0) \rangle = \{(m, 0); m \in R\}$, $N = \langle (0, 1) \rangle = \{(0, n); n \in R\}$ are two subspaces of $V = R^2$.

(b) $T = M + NI_1 + MI_2 = \{(m, 0) + (0, n)I_1 + (s, 0)I_2; m, n, s \in R\}$ is a weak AH-subspace of $V_2(I)$.

(c) The set $X = \{(1, 0), (0, 1)I_1, (1, 0)I_2\}$ is a bases of T , $\dim(T) = \dim(M) + \dim(N) + \dim(M) = 3$.

(d) $D = N + NI_1 + NI_2 = \{(0, a) + (0, b)I_1 + (0, c)I_2; a, b, c \in R\}$ is a weak AHS-subspace.

Theorem 3.5:

Let V be a vector space with $\dim(V) = n + 1$. Then V is isomorphic to a weak AHS-subspace of the corresponding weak n -refined neutrosophic vector space.

Proof:

Let M be any one dimensional subspace of V , $T = M + MI_1 + \dots + MI_n$ is a weak AHS-subspace of the weak n -refined neutrosophic vector space $V_n(I)$. As a result of Theorem 3.3, we find $\dim(T) = n + 1 = \dim(V)$, thus V is isomorphic to T .

Example 3.6:

Let $V = R^3$ be a vector space over the field R , $V_3(I) = \{a + bI_1 + cI_2 + dI_3; a, b, c, d \in V\}$ is the corresponding weak 3-refined neutrosophic vector space, $M = \langle (1, 0, 0) \rangle$ is a subspace of V .

$T = M + MI_1 + MI_2 = \{(a, 0, 0) + (b, 0, 0)I_1 + (c, 0, 0)I_2; a, b, c \in R\}$ is a weak AHS-subspace of $V_3(I)$ with $\dim(T) = 3$, this implies $T \cong V$.

Theorem 3.7:

Let $(V, +, \cdot)$ be a vector space over a field K , $V_n(I)$ be the corresponding strong n -refined neutrosophic vector space over the n -refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, $M_n(I) = M + MI_1 + \dots + MI_n$ be a strong n -refined AHS-subspace. Then:

(a) $M_n(I)$ is a submodule of $V_n(I)$.

(b) If Y is a bases of M , $X = \cup_{i=0}^n YI_i$ is a bases of $M_n(I)$.

(c) $\dim(M_n(I)) = \sum_{i=0}^n \dim(M) = n \cdot \dim(M)$.

Proof:

(a) Let $x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i, y = \sum_{i=0}^n b_i I_i; b_i, a_i \in M_i$ be two arbitrary elements in $M_n(I)$, $r = \sum_{i=0}^n r_i I_i$ be an arbitrary element in $K_n(I)$, we have:

$x + y = \sum_{i=0}^n (a_i + b_i) I_i \in M_n(I)$, since $a_i + b_i \in M_i$ because M_i is a subspace of V .

$r \cdot x = \sum_{i,j=0}^n r_i a_j I_i I_j \in M_n(I)$, since $r_i a_j \in M$ because M is a subspace of V . Thus $M_n(I)$ is a vector subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b),(c) They are similar to that of Theorem 3.5 .

Remark 3.8:

If $V_n(I)$ is a strong n-refined neutrosophic vector space over the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, and

$M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1 I_1 + \dots + M_n I_n$ is a strong n-refined AH-subspace, then it is not supposed to be a submodule.

We clarify it by the following example.

Example 3.9:

Let $V = R^2$ be a vector space over R , $V_2(I) = R_2^2(I) = \{(a, b) + (c, d)I_1 + (e, f)I_2; a, b, c, d, e, f \in R\}$ be the corresponding strong 2-refined neutrosophic vector space over the neutrosophic field $R_2(I)$.

$M = \langle 0, 1 \rangle, N = \langle (1, 0) \rangle$ are two subspaces of V , $T = M + NI_1 + NI_2$ is a strong AH-subspace of $V_2(I)$.

$x = (0, 1) + (2, 0)I_1 + (1, 0)I_2 \in T, r = 1 + 1 \cdot I_1 + 1 \cdot I_2 \in R_2(I)$,

$r \cdot x = 1 \cdot (0, 1) + 1 \cdot (0, 1)I_1 + 1 \cdot (0, 1)I_2 + 1 \cdot (2, 0)I_1 I_1 + 1 \cdot (2, 0)I_1 + 1 \cdot (1, 0)I_1 I_2 + 1 \cdot (0, 1)I_2 + 1 \cdot (2, 0)I_1 I_2 + 1 \cdot (2, 0)I_2 I_2 = (0, 1) + [(0, 1) + (2, 0) + (1, 0) + (2, 0)]I_1 + [(0, 1) + (0, 1) + (2, 0)]I_2 =$

$(0, 1) + (5, 1)I_1 + (2, 2)I_2$, $r \cdot x$ does not belong to T , thus T is not a submodule.

Definition 3.10:

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak/strong n-refined neutrosophic vector space, $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1 I_1 + \dots + M_n I_n$,

$W_n(I) = W_0 + W_1 I_1 + \dots + W_n I_n$ be two weak/strong AH-subspaces of $V_n(I)$, we define:

(a) $M_n(I) \cap W_n(I) = (M_0 \cap W_0) + (M_1 \cap W_1)I_1 + \dots + (M_n \cap W_n)I_n$.

(b) $M_n(I) + W_n(I) = (M_0 + W_0) + (M_1 + W_1)I_1 + \dots + (M_n + W_n)I_n$.

Theorem 3.11:

Let $V_n(I)$ be a weak n-refined neutrosophic vector space, $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1 I_1 + \dots + M_n I_n$,

$W_n(I) = W_0 + W_1 I_1 + \dots + W_n I_n$ be two weak AH-subspaces of $V_n(I)$. Then:

$M_n(I) \cap W_n(I), M_n(I) + W_n(I)$ are two weak AH-subspaces of $V_n(I)$.

Proof:

Since $M_i \cap W_i, M_i + W_i$ are subspaces of V for all i , we obtain the proof.

Theorem 3.12:

Let $V_n(I)$ be a strong n -refined neutrosophic vector space, $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n$,

$W_n(I) = W_0 + W_1I_1 + \dots + W_nI_n$ be two strong AH-subspaces of $V_n(I)$. Then:

- (a) $M_n(I) \cap W_n(I)$ is a strong AH-subspaces of $V_n(I)$.
- (b) $M_n(I) + W_n(I)$ is not supposed to be a strong AH-subspace of $V_n(I)$.

Proof:

The proof is similar to that of Theorem 3.11 .

Definition 3.13:

Let V, W be two vector spaces over the field K , $f_i: V \rightarrow W; 0 \leq i \leq n+1$ be $n+1$ linear transformations, $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be the corresponding weak n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the field K respectively. We say:

- (a) $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ is a weak AH-linear transformation.
- (b) If $f_i = f_j$ for all i, j , we call f a weak AHS-linear transformation.

Example 3.14:

(a) Let $V = R^3, W = R^2$ be two vector spaces over the field R , $V_2(I) = R_2^3(I) = \{ (x_0, y_0, z_0) + (x_1, y_1, z_1)I_1 + (x_2, y_2, z_2)I_2; x_i, y_i, z_i \in R \}$,

$W_2(I) = \{ (x_0, y_0) + (x_1, y_1)I_1 + (x_2, y_2)I_2; x_i, y_i \in R \}$ be the corresponding weak 2-refined neutrosophic vector spaces. We have $g: V \rightarrow W; g(a, b, c) = (b, c), h: V \rightarrow W; h(a, b, c) = (2a, 0)$

$s: V \rightarrow W; s(a, b, c) = (2b, 3c)$ are three linear transformations.

(b) $f: V_2(I) \rightarrow W_2(I); f(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + h(n)I_1 + s(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a weak AH-linear transformation.

(c) We clarify f as follows:

$$x = (1, 2, 2) + (1, 0, 1)I_1 + (3, -1, 0)I_2 \in V_2(I),$$

$$f(x) = g(1, 2, 2) + [h(1, 0, 1)]I_1 + [s(3, -1, 0)]I_2 = (2, 2) + (2, 0)I_1 + (-2, 0)I_2.$$

(d) $k: V_2(I) \rightarrow W_2(I); k(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + g(n)I_1 + g(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a weak AHS-linear transformation.

Definition 3.15:

Let V, W be two vector spaces over the field K , $f_i: V \rightarrow W; 0 \leq i \leq n+1$ be $n+1$ linear transformations, $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be the corresponding strong n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the n -refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$ respectively. We say:

(a) $f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ is a strong AH-linear transformation.

(b) If $f_i = f_j$ for all i, j , we call f a strong AHS-linear transformation.

Example 3.16:

(a) Let $V = R^3, W = R^2$ be two vector spaces over the field R , $V_2(I) = R_2^3(I) = \{(x_0, y_0, z_0) + (x_1, y_1, z_1)I_1 + (x_2, y_2, z_2)I_2; x_i, y_i, z_i \in R\}$,

$W_2(I) = \{(x_0, y_0) + (x_1, y_1)I_1 + (x_2, y_2)I_2; x_i, y_i \in R\}$ be the corresponding strong 2-refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the 2-refined neutrosophic field $R_2(I)$. We have $g: V \rightarrow W; g(a, b, c) = (b, c), h: V \rightarrow W; h(a, b, c) = (2a, 0)$,

$s: V \rightarrow W; s(a, b, c) = (2b, 3c)$ are three linear transformations.

(b) $f: V_2(I) \rightarrow W_2(I); f(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + h(n)I_1 + s(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a strong AH-linear transformation.

(c) We clarify f as follows:

$$x = (1, 2, 2) + (1, 0, 1)I_1 + (3, -1, 0)I_2 \in V_2(I),$$

$$f(x) = g(1, 2, 2) + [h(1, 0, 1)]I_1 + [s(3, -1, 0)]I_2 = (2, 2) + (2, 0)I_1 + (-2, 0)I_2.$$

(d) $k: V_2(I) \rightarrow W_2(I); k(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + g(n)I_1 + g(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a strong AHS-linear transformation.

Definition 3.17:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two weak/strong n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces,

$f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ be a weak/strong AH-linear transformation. We define:

(a) $AH - Ker(f) = Ker(f_0) + Ker(f_1)I_1 + \dots + Ker(f_n)I_n.$

(b) $AH - Im(f) = Im(f_0) + Im(f_1)I_1 + \dots + Im(f_n)I_n.$

Theorem 3.18:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two weak n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces,

$f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ be a weak AH-linear transformation. Then:

(a) $AH - Ker(f)$ is a weak AH-subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) $AH - Im(f)$ is a weak AH-subspace of $W_n(I)$.

(c) If $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n$ is a weak AH-subspace of $V_n(I)$, $f(M_n(I))$ is a weak AH-subspace of $W_n(I)$.

Proof:

(a) Since $\text{Ker}(f_i)$ is a subspace of V , we find that

$$AH - \text{Ker}(f) = \text{Ker}(f_0) + \text{Ker}(f_1)I_1 + \dots + \text{Ker}(f_n)I_n \text{ is a weak AH-subspace of } V_n(I).$$

(b) Since $\text{Im}(f_i)$ is a subspace of W , we find that $AH - \text{Im}(f) = \text{Im}(f_0) + \text{Im}(f_1)I_1 + \dots + \text{Im}(f_n)I_n$ is a weak AH-subspace of $W_n(I)$.

(c) It is known that $f_i(M_i)$ is a subspace of W , hence

$$f(M_n(I)) = f_0(M_0) + f_1(M_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(M_n)I_n \text{ is a weak AH-subspace of } W_n(I).$$

Theorem 3.19:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two strong n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the n -refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$,

$f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ be a strong AH-linear transformation. Then:

(a) $AH - \text{Ker}(f)$ is a strong AH-subspace of $V_n(I)$.

(b) $AH - \text{Im}(f)$ is a strong AH-subspace of $W_n(I)$.

(c) If $M_n(I) = M_0 + M_1I_1 + \dots + M_nI_n$ is a strong AH-subspace of $V_n(I)$, $f(M_n(I))$ is a strong AH-subspace of $W_n(I)$.

Proof:

The proof is similar to that of Theorem 3.18 .

Example 3.20:

Let $V_2(I), W_2(I)$ be the two weak 2-refined neutrosophic vector spaces defined in Example 3.16 .

(a) $M = \langle (1,0,0) \rangle, N = \langle (0,1,0) \rangle, L = \langle (0,0,1) \rangle$ are three subspaces of V ,

$T = M + NI_1 + LI_2 = \{(a, 0, 0) + (0, b, 0)I_1 + (0, 0, c)I_2; a, b, c \in R\}$ is a weak AH-subspace of $V_2(I)$.

Consider $f: V_2(I) \rightarrow W_2(I)$ the weak AH-linear transformation defined in Example 3.16 .

(b) $AH - \text{Ker}(f) = \text{Ker}(g) + \text{Ker}(h)I_1 + \text{Ker}(s)I_2 = \{(a, 0, 0) + (0, b, c)I_1 + (d, 0, 0)I_2; a, b, c, d \in R$.

(c) $AH - \text{Im}(f) = \text{Im}(g) + \text{Im}(h)I_1 + \text{Im}(s)I_2 = R^2 + \langle (1,0) \rangle I_1 + R^2 I_2$.

(d) $f(T) = g(M) + h(N)I_1 + s(L)I_2 = \langle (0,0) \rangle + \langle (0,0) \rangle I_1 + \langle (0,1) \rangle I_2 =$

$\{(0,0) + (0,0).I_1 + (0, a)I_2; a \in R\}$, which is a weak AH-subspace of $W_2(I)$.

Theorem 3.21:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two weak n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the field K ,

$f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ be a weak AH-linear transformation. Then:

$$f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y), f(r \cdot x) = r \cdot f(x) \text{ for all } x, y \in V_n(I), r \in K.$$

Proof:

Let $x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i, y = \sum_{i=0}^n b_i I_i$ be two arbitrary elements in $V_n(I), r \in K$ be any element in the field K , we have:

$$f(x + y) = f(\sum_{i=0}^n (a_i + b_i)I_i) = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i + b_i)I_i = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i + \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(b_i)I_i = f(x) + f(y).$$

$$f(r \cdot x) = f(\sum_{i=0}^n r a_i I_i) = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(r a_i)I_i = r \cdot \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i = r \cdot f(x).$$

Theorem 3.22:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I)$ be two strong n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$,

$f: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i$ be a strong AH-linear transformation. Then:

$$f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y), f(r \cdot x) = r \cdot f(x) \text{ for all } x, y \in V_n(I), r \in K_n(I).$$

Proof:

Let $x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i, y = \sum_{i=0}^n b_i I_i$ be two arbitrary elements in $V_n(I), r = \sum_{i=0}^n r_i I_i \in K_n(I)$ be any element in the n-refined neutrosophic field $K_n(I)$, we have:

$$f(x + y) = f(\sum_{i=0}^n (a_i + b_i)I_i) = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i + b_i)I_i = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i + \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(b_i)I_i = f(x) + f(y).$$

For the proof of the second proposition we use induction on n. If $n=0$, the theorem is true clearly.

Suppose that it is true for $n-1$, we must prove it for n .

$f(r \cdot x) = f(\sum_{i,j=0}^n r_i a_j I_i I_j) = f(\sum_{i,j=0}^{n-1} r_i a_j I_i I_j + (\sum_{i=0}^n r_i I_i) a_n I_n)$, we can write

$$\sum_{i,j=0}^{n-1} r_i a_j I_i I_j = m_0 + m_1 I_1 + \dots + m_{n-1} I_{n-1},$$

$$(\sum_{i=0}^n r_i I_i) a_n I_n = r_1 a_n I_1 + r_2 a_n I_2 + \dots + (r_0 a_n + r_n a_n) I_n,$$

$$r \cdot x = \sum_{i,j=0}^{n-1} r_i a_j I_i I_j + (\sum_{i=0}^n r_i I_i) a_n I_n = m_0 + (m_1 + r_1 a_n) I_1 + (m_2 + r_2 a_n) I_2 + \dots + (r_0 a_n + r_n a_n) I_n,$$

$$f(r \cdot x) = f_0(m_0) + f_1(m_1 + r_1 a_n) I_1 + f_2(m_2 + r_2 a_n) I_2 + \dots + f_n(r_0 a_n + r_n a_n) I_n =$$

$$f_0(m_0) + [f_1(m_1) + r_1 f_1(a_n)] I_1 + \dots + [r_0 f_n(a_n) + r_n f_n(a_n)] I_n = r \cdot f(x).$$

Theorem 3.23:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I), U_n(I)$ be three weak n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the field K ,

$f: W_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i)I_i,$

$g: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); g(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = g_0(a_0) + g_1(a_1)I_1 + \dots + g_n(a_n)I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n g_i(a_i)I_i,$

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be two weak AH-linear transformations. Then:

$$(a) f \circ g = \sum_{i=0}^n (f_i \circ g_i).$$

(b) $f \circ g$ is a weak AH-linear transformation between $V_n(I), U_n(I)$.

Proof:

$$(a) \text{ Let } x = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i \in V_n(I), f \circ g(x) = f(\sum_{i=0}^n g_i(a_i) I_i) = f(g_0(a_0) + g_1(a_1) I_1 + \dots + g_n(a_n) I_n) =$$

$$f_0(g_0(a_0)) + f_1(g_1(a_1)) I_1 + \dots + f_n(g_n(a_n)) I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n (f_i \circ g_i)(a_i) I_i.$$

(b) Since $f_i \circ g_i$ is a linear transformation for all i , then we get the proof.

Theorem 3.24:

Let $V_n(I), W_n(I), U_n(I)$ be three strong n -refined neutrosophic vector spaces over the n -refined neutrosophic field K ,

$$f: W_n(I) \rightarrow U_n(I); f(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = f_0(a_0) + f_1(a_1) I_1 + \dots + f_n(a_n) I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n f_i(a_i) I_i,$$

$$g: V_n(I) \rightarrow W_n(I); g(\sum_{i=0}^n a_i I_i) = g_0(a_0) + g_1(a_1) I_1 + \dots + g_n(a_n) I_n = \sum_{i=0}^n g_i(a_i) I_i,$$

be two strong AH-linear transformations. Then:

$$(a) f \circ g = \sum_{i=0}^n (f_i \circ g_i).$$

(b) $f \circ g$ is a strong AH-linear transformation between $V_n(I), U_n(I)$.

Proof:

The proof is similar to that of Theorem 3.23.

Example 3.25:

$$(a) \text{ Let } V = R^3 \text{ be a vector spaces over the field } R, V_2(I) = R_2^3(I) = \{(x_0, y_0, z_0) + (x_1, y_1, z_1) I_1 + (x_2, y_2, z_2) I_2; x_i, y_i, z_i \in R\},$$

be the corresponding weak 2-refined neutrosophic vector space. We have $g: V \rightarrow V; g(a, b, c) = (2b, 2c, 0)$,

$$h: V \rightarrow V; h(a, b, c) = (2a, c, c),$$

$s: V \rightarrow V; s(a, b, c) = (2b, 3c, a)$ are three linear transformations.

(b) $f: V_2(I) \rightarrow V_2(I); f(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + h(n)I_1 + s(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a weak AH-linear transformation, $j: V_2(I) \rightarrow V_2(I); j(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g(m) + g(n)I_1 + h(q)I_2; m, n, q \in V$ is a weak AH-linear transformation.

$$(c) f \circ j(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g \circ g(m) + h \circ g(n)I_1 + s \circ h(q)I_2.$$

(d) Put $m = (2, 1, 0), n = (-1, 0, 0), q = (3, 2, 2)$, we compute $f \circ j$ as follows:

$$f \circ j(m + nI_1 + qI_2) = g \circ g[(2, 1, 0)] + h \circ g[(-1, 0, 0)]I_1 + s \circ h[(3, 2, 2)]I_2 =$$

$$g(2, 0, 0) + h(0, 0, 0)I_1 + s(6, 2, 2)I_2 = (0, 0, 0) + (0, 0, 0)I_1 + (4, 6, 6)I_2.$$

5. Conclusion

In this paper we have defined and studied weak/strong AH-subspaces and weak/strong AH-linear transformations in n-refined neutrosophic vector spaces. Also, we have presented some elementary properties and theorems about these concepts.

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References

- [1] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Neutrosophic Rings and Their Properties", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 4 , pp. 72-81, 2020.
- [2] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Refined Neutrosophic Rings", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 5, pp. 59-66, 2020.
- [3] Abobala, M., "Classical Homomorphisms Between Refined Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Rings", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 5, pp. 72-75, 2020.
- [4] Abobala, M., " AH-subspaces in Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", *International Journal of neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 6 , pp. 80-86, 2020.
- [5] Abobala, M., " Classical Homomorphisms Between n-Refined neutrosophic Rings", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 7 , pp. 74-78, 2020.
- [6] Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., "Refined Neutrosophic Rings II", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 2, pp. 89-94, 2020.
- [7] Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., "Refined Neutrosophic Rings I", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 2 , pp. 77-81, 2020.
- [8] Agboola, A.A.A., and Akinleye, S.A., "Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 4 , pp. 9-17, 2014.
- [9] Agboola, A.A.A., Akwu, A.D., and Oyebo, Y.T., "Neutrosophic Groups and Subgroups", *International J .Math.Combin*, Vol. 3, pp. 1-9, 2012.
- [10] Agboola, A.A.A., Akinola, A.D., and Oyebola, O.Y., " NeutrosophicRings I ", *International J.Mathcombin*, Vol. 4, pp. 1-14, 2011.
- [11] T. Bera., and N. K. Mahapatra., *On Neutrosophic Soft Field*, *IJMTT*, 56(7), pp. 472-494, 2018.
- [12] T. Bera., and N. K. Mahapatra., *On Neutrosophic Soft Linear Spaces*, *Fuzzy Information and Engineering.*, 9, 299-324, (2017).
- [13] Injrou, S., "Linear Algebra 2 ", *Tishreen University Press*, pp 180-230, 2015.

[14] Kandasamy, V.W.B., and Smarandache, F., "Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Neutrosophic N-Algebraic Structures", Hexis, Phonex, Arizona 2006.

[15] Smarandache, F., and Abobala, M., "n-Refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 6, pp. 83-90 , 2020.

[16] Smarandache F., and Abobala, M., "n-Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 47-54, 2020.